

Challenges and solutions of using authentic materials for improving students' productive competences in English language learning

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Annotatsiya. Ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'qitish turli xil o'qitish usullari, yondashuvlari va texnikasi bilan ajoyib ish deb hisoblanadi. Bu jarayonda autentik materiallardan foydalanish o'qitish va o'rganish jarayonini yanada qiziqarli va jonli qiladi. Shunga qaramay, o'qituvchilar ulardan foydalanishda turli qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishlari mumkin. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tili sinflarida autentik materiallardan foydalanishda yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan qiyinchiliklarni o'rganib chiqildi va ularni hal qilishning muhim yo'llarini taklif qilishga harakat qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: autentik materiallar, haqiqiylik, foyda, nutqni o'rgatish, yozishni o'rgatish, til o'rganuvchilar.

Abstract. Teaching English as a foreign language is assumed that as great job with various teaching methods, approaches and techniques. In this process, using authentic materials makes teaching and learning process more interesting and vibrant. Even though, teachers may face various challenges using them. This article is researched that possible difficulties of utilizing authentic materials in English classrooms and tried to suggest substantial solutions to them.

Key words: authentic materials, authenticity, benefits, teaching speaking, teaching writing, language learners.

Аннотация. Преподавание английского языка как иностранного предполагает большую работу с использованием различных методов, подходов и приемов обучения. При этом использование аутентичных материалов делает процесс преподавания и обучения более интересным и

ярким. Несмотря на это, учителя могут столкнуться с различными проблемами при их использовании. В этой статье были исследованы возможные трудности использования аутентичных материалов на занятиях по английскому языку и предпринята попытка предложить существенные решения этих проблем.

Ключевые слова: аутентичные материалы, аутентичность, преимущества, обучение говорению, обучение письму, изучающие язык.

The use of authentic materials can have a beneficial impact on students' productive competences and specifically speaking and writing skills. To include authentic materials into English language lessons effectively, it is important to follow several linguodidactic principles regarding the choice of materials. Authenticity represents the first principle, meaning that the use of real language in real communicative situations should be reflected in the chosen materials. Examples of authentic materials are newspapers, magazines, advertisements, podcasts, videos, songs, or even posts on social media. Authenticity allows students to understand language forms, idiomatic expressions, and cultural-specific connotations. Relevance is another principle that means that authentic materials should reflect learners' interests, needs, and proficiency levels. It will encourage learners to acquire new knowledge and make new connections. Additionally, it is significant to take into account learners' age, cultural background, and personal preferences. In addition to this teacher should create tasks or activities that foster students' engagement with authentic materials in task-based language teaching. A possible activity following the listening to a podcast or a video might be a formal discussion, role-play, or a debate on the subjects touched in the source. Such approach allows students to communicate meaningfully and mobilize their language resources.

Using authentic materials is considered as a language awareness to draw students' attention to the language they have encountered, such as vocabulary, grammar patterns, or discourse rules. Students should reflect on the contextual use of a particular linguistic feature and select the features which are applicable to their own communicative objectives.

The cultural context of the authentic materials can help students develop cultural awareness and intercultural understanding. Particularly, they can compare and

contrast cultural aspects in the target language and their primary language by discussing the authentic texts in class. Thus, the students develop empathy and social interactions. Teachers can modify adapted authentic materials to cater to all students' varied needs and learning styles. But they should scaffold and assist as necessary, more so when dealing with students with limited-proficiency levels and provide advanced students with extension and enrichment moves to push the limits of their learning. However, there are many problems when authentic materials are used for writing instruction in EFL classes. Such problems can be solved by various strategies and solutions. Authentic materials could be either too complex or not adapted to EFL students' proficiency levels. They include language structures, vocabulary, and cultural references that EFL students cannot fully understand or use, which could result in comprehension problems and lack of motivation. Some authentic materials might not be available for particular age group of EFL writers. For example, newspapers and magazines are not always in open access, and many young EFL language professionals may have limited online subscriptions. Furthermore, certain books in English are not translated into other languages, and EFL writing students from non-English-speaking countries may be prohibited from using digital resources.

Cultural disconnect is one of the crucial problem for EFL learners and they may lack the background knowledge necessary to understand the cultural specifics behind an authentic text, including references or various context-specific details. It reduces their chances of identifying with the material and producing their culturally appropriate writing.

By addressing these issues with specific solutions, EFL teachers may effectively use authentic resources to improve students' writing skills, linguistic competency, and cultural competence.

When teachers implement the real resources into teaching speaking in EFL classrooms, they may face many problems, as well as solutions to overcome them. When using authentic materials in speaking exercises, EFL learners may feel frightened or lack confidence, especially if they believe the language is too difficult or unfamiliar. Furthermore authentic materials like audio recordings or movies may provide few opportunities for interactive speaking practice, especially in classrooms with large student populations or limited resources.

Selecting authentic resources are appropriate for students' competency levels and interests, and then adjust them as needed to reduce linguistic complexity while maintaining authenticity and providing scaffolding, such as pre-teaching is important for vocabulary or phrases, to assist understanding and spoken communication. Language and cultural ideas should be taught related to the real material ahead of time to help students understand and feel more confident. They should be simplified or adjusted the information to meet the learners' competency levels while remaining authentic.

Interactive Speaking Tasks are thought that for creating speaking exercises that encourage student participation and cooperation. They can be include role-playing, debates, simulations, and pair/group discussions to provide students plenty of opportunity to practice speaking in genuine settings.

Guided Practice is also advisable via dividing the real information into digestible chunks and offer guided practice exercises to assist students comprehend and absorb language structures, vocabulary, and cultural allusions. Cultural knowledge should be provided to increase cultural knowledge and sensitivity by addressing cultural elements embedded in real content. Encouraging students to express their thoughts and experiences, impacts on resulting in a better knowledge of cultural differences and commonalities.

Pronunciation practice is considered as the biggest challenge by many language learners so teacher should try to incorporate targeted pronunciation practice into speaking activities, emphasizing difficult consonants, stress patterns, and intonation. In this situation drills, tongue twisters, and repetition exercises can help language learners develop their pronunciation abilities gradually. Addressing these problems with specific solutions allows EFL teachers to effectively use the benefits of authentic resources to improve students' speaking abilities, fluency, cultural competency, and confidence in using English in real-world circumstances.

CONCLUSION

Utilizing authentic materials in reaching writing and speaking skills requires carefulness by the teacher although they have various advantages for teaching process. Both teachers and language learners can face various challenges when implementing real materials to the lesson. Authentic materials can inform the learners about real life situations and using the authentic language and in short they

feel the target language fully by real materials. In the same time they may have a difficulty with cultural differences, complex language structures or unfamiliar vocabulary. But teachers should prevent expected problems in advance or try to solve them effectively. They should choose authentic materials according to learners' age, level and other factors and undoubtedly they meet the learners' needs. Then teacher achieve to a lesson objectives and the students engagement to the lesson easily.

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